

THE DEVELOPMENT OF RAILWAY TRANSPORT AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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ANNOTATION *The article provides information about the emergence of railway transport and its introduction into Central Asia. Also, it was analyzed that during the years of independence, unprecedented works were carried out in the field of development of railway transport, economy and technology, as a result of efficient management of resources, along with all types of transport in Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *discovery, railway, efficiency, economy, independence.*

АННОТАЦИЯ *В статье представлена информация о появлении железнодорожного транспорта и его внедрении в Среднюю Азию. Также было проанализировано, что за годы независимости были проведены беспрецедентные работы в области развития железнодорожного транспорта, экономики и техники, как результат эффективного управления ресурсами, наряду со всеми видами транспорта в Узбекистане.*

Ключевые слова: *открытие, железная дорога, эффективность, экономика, независимость.*

INTRODUCTION

In the history of mankind, "In 1814, the English designer and inventor George Stephenson created the first steam engine. When the steam locomotive was tested on the railway track, it traveled at a speed of 10 km per hour, pulling 8 wagons... In 1825, George Stephenson managed to build the first railway between two cities. 1825 is indicated as the date of appearance of the first railway transport in many literatures. But as can be seen from the above quote, on this date, a railway was built between the two cities and railway traffic was started. Therefore,

in our opinion, it is correct to say that the intercity railway connection was established in 1825 and the mass use of this type of transport began¹.

Construction of the first railway to the territory of Central Asia was carried out in 1880 in the direction from the Caspian Sea to Kyzyl Arbot, and it was completed in 1881. This railway, which remained in history under the name of Kaspiyorti (Zakaspiy), was delivered to Ashgabat in 1885, and to Chorjoi in 1886. Two years later, in May 1888, trains to Samarkand began². In 1896, the initial part of the railway was moved to the port city of Krasnovodsk, which could receive large ships. The railway that reached Samarkand was continued from there. At Ursatevsk (now Khovos) station, the road splits into two. One to Tashkent, the other to the Fergana Valley. Both routes were completed in 1899. In 1900, the Marv-Kushka railway was launched in the southern direction. In this way, important strategic regions of Central Asia were covered by railway.

MAIN PART

In 1901, the construction of the Orenburg-Tashkent railway began. Construction started on both sides was completed in January 1906, and thus Central Asia joined the railway network for the first time with other regions. It should be noted that this road was of great importance in the lives of the peoples of Central Asia. The peoples of the region, including Uzbekistan, are still using this road. The launch of the Orenburg-Tashkent railway has further increased the trade and freight traffic between Russia and its former colony, the Central Asian region. Naturally, the amount of cotton goods taken from the region increased. It should be

¹ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

² Салимов Б. Л., Бобожонов О., Рўзимбоев Ж. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНГА ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ КИРИБ КЕЛИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ – ФАЛСАФИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 153–158.

noted that the railway and railway transport, that is, steam locomotives, were a novelty for the local people.³

In 1917, the government of the Soviets, which came to power in place of the Russian Empire, fundamentally changed the country's economy from the first years. He introduced completely new ways of doing business. Ownership of property took on a new form and meaning. Private ownership was completely abandoned, and its place was taken by the form of collective, or rather, state ownership. All sectors were fully and directly controlled by the state. Including railway transport. Of course, this policy had its own negative and positive consequences⁴. It can be said without hesitation that during the former union, along with all other types of transport, railway transport has developed significantly. Since the 1920s, reconstruction, reconstruction and repair work has been carried out in most of the Central Asian railways. Together with these works, the construction of new railway lines was started. The connection of the Turkestan-Siberia railway with the length of 1452 km, which remained in history under the name "Turksib" and was commissioned in 1929-1931, with the railway of Uzbekistan was also of great importance in the development of the region.

Along with the development of railways, locomotives and wagons moving on it were also improved. During this period, the movement of new EU-style steam locomotives will be launched on the railways of Uzbekistan. The power, speed and other technical capabilities of steam locomotives of this type were much higher than their predecessors⁵. This had an effect on increasing the efficiency of railway transport. Also, in these years, steam locomotives, which are superior to steam

³ Салимов Б. Л., Бобожонов О., Рўзимбоев Ж. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНГА ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ КИРИБ КЕЛИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ – ФАЛСАФИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 153–158.

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

⁵ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

locomotives in terms of efficiency, began to be used on the railways of Central Asia. In the world experience, the first passenger and cargo transportation by locomotive-hauled trains was launched on the Central Asian Railway in 1931 on the routes Ashgabat - Dushak and Ashgabat - Bamu. A new branch of railway transport in Central Asia has begun to emerge: wagon building. For the first time in 1935, wagon repair stations were built at Termez, Karshi and Hovost stations. Wagon depots were built in the cities of Samarkand, Kogon, and Kogon. The construction of these production and repair enterprises became important in meeting the need for wagons necessary for the operation of the Central Asian railway transport. The development of the carriage service industry continued in the following years. In the future, it served as a solid foundation for establishing its own wagon-making industry in independent Uzbekistan⁶.

The establishment of a railway network across the Central Asian region connected with other allied republics was of great importance in the victory of the former USSR state in the Great Patriotic War of 1941-1945. Hundreds of thousands of people and hundreds of industrial enterprises were evacuated to Uzbekistan by railways from the areas threatened by the enemy. More than a million of our forefathers went to fight fiercely against the enemy through these roads. Also, weapons, clothing, food and other necessary things needed for the front were sent by railways.

It is known that "the normative component of the procedure is connected with the field of practice. Its obvious spheres of influence are economics and technology⁷. The principle of leadership in them is optimal and efficient management of resources. If we take it in this sense, we will not be mistaken if we say that during the years of independence, railway transport, along with all types of

⁶ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

⁷ Салимов Б. Л., Бобожонов О., Рўзимбоев Ж. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНГА ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ КИРИБ КЕЛИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ – ФАЛСАФИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований, 1 (6), 153–158.

transport in Uzbekistan, reached its literal peak of growth. As a result of optimal and effective management of resources aimed at improving the economy and technology, during the years of independence, unprecedented work was carried out in the field, and a unified railway system was created in Uzbekistan. Although independence is a great value, a number of problems faced the countries that have gained independence⁸. In particular, the inconveniences caused by road and communication issues put the countries in a very difficult situation. The most important of these was the transfer of the existing roads and railways connecting the country's territories to the territory of the neighboring countries. This problem also appeared in Uzbekistan. Part of the railway leading to Karakalpakstan and Khorezm and Surkhandarya region remained in the territory of Turkmenistan, and the railway connecting with Ferghana Valley remained in the territory of Tajikistan. These countries, which are rightly our neighbors and brothers, did not obstruct the movement of our trains in their territories. However, they allowed it under certain conditions. A large price was charged as transit for each wagon. This led to a decrease in the economic efficiency of our passenger and freight trains running on these roads. Then, in this place, the issue of security was always on the agenda. When our trains are running in the territory of a foreign country, various dangers and illegal acts are more likely to occur. Therefore, train sets were kept for hours for inspection at border-customs posts⁹. Especially those on passenger trains suffered a lot. Those who rode passenger trains at that time probably know well that our trains traveling through the territory of neighboring countries were stopped and inspected four times: the first, when leaving our territory; the second, when entering the territory of a neighboring country; the third, when leaving the territory of a neighboring country; fourth, when entering the territory of our country. It took

⁸ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

⁹ Салимов Б. Л., Бобожонов О., Рўзимбоев Ж. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНГА ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ КИРИБ КЕЛИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ – ФАЛСАФИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований, 1 (6), 153–158.

four hours when it left one hour, and eight hours when it left two hours. So, movement through neighboring countries was inefficient in all respects¹⁰. The only way to solve this problem was to build new railways connecting regions in our territory. It should be noted that Uzbekistan was able to successfully solve this problem step by step. For this purpose, during the past years, new railway construction works were carried out in three directions, in unique conditions.

With the commissioning of the construction of the Angren-Pop electrified railway, the railway coverage of all regions of our country was practically completed. Thus, the total length of railways in our country reached 6500 kilometers. But the work did not stop there. Another important task of electrification of railways was put before our railway workers. The process of electrification of the railways of Uzbekistan is being continued at a rapid pace these days. After all, the electrification of railways has many advantages. First of all, electric locomotives are more reliable, convenient and efficient than diesel locomotives. There are more opportunities for the country to produce electricity than to produce petroleum products. Of course, there are also ecological issues. Because the indicators of environmental pollution of electric locomotives are also low¹¹.

CONCLUSION

When it comes to electric locomotives, the high-speed electric train "Afrosiyob", which has been running since October 8, 2011, on the Tashkent-Samarkand-Tashkent (currently Tashkent-Bukhara-Tashkent) route, comes to mind. After all, all comforts for passengers have been created in this electric train. It is difficult to describe these amenities in words. Those who have been to it even

¹⁰Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

¹¹ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

once as a passenger will feel it in their bodies. The softness of the seats of the electric train, the insensitivity when moving at high speed, the fact that outside noise does not penetrate inside, the high level of services provided to passengers in the carriage, and other amenities are excellent. The most important thing is that if you used to go to the destination in 5-6 hours, you will reach the destination in a little more than two hours on the high-speed electric train "Afrosiyab". All this is a vivid expression of the creative changes taking place in railway transport. There is no doubt that in the near future electric trains similar to the "Afrosiyob" high-speed electric train will be launched on all railway lines of Uzbekistan.

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